

Giant leaking pseudoaneurysm in an intravenous drug user

Ahmad Uzair Qureshi¹, Neela Gumbad¹

Correspondence: Ahmad Uzair Qureshi, Mayo Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan. Email: ahmeduzairq@gmail.com

In many low- and middle-income countries, unsafe intravenous drug use is common, and patients often present with thigh lesions that resemble infected abscesses. Repeated trauma to the femoral artery during injections into the femoral vein can lead to the formation of infected pseudoaneurysms, which users sometimes exploit as large “ports” for easier drug administration. These lesions typically come to medical attention only once they begin to leak. By that stage, the surrounding soft-tissue infection and active bleeding make primary excision and reconstruction unfeasible. Definitive management therefore requires urgent wide local debridement and high ligation of the affected vessels, followed by extra-anatomical revascularisation.

Conflicts of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest and no funding has been accepted for the publication.

Consent: The authors confirm that they hold obtained written informed consent from the patient for the publication of this case report and accompanying images.

¹ King Edward Medical University, Lahore, Pakistan

Cite as: Qureshi, A. U. ., & Gumbad, N. Giant leaking pseudoaneurysm in an intravenous drug user. *Impact Surgery*, 2(5), 178. <https://doi.org/10.62463/surgery.186>